

Bhrigu's and Saturn

65 Comments / Blog / By Deepanshu Giri

In our chart, there are possibilities of several hundred yogas present applicable, and as an astrologer, it is pretty challenging to remember more than 30-40 yogas or combinations and their results, as that is why most of the astrologers stick to classical famous yogas such as Budh-Aditya yoga or Gajkesari Yog, but if one can understand the core concept of Nadi or Bhrigu yogas, you will find it is not only easy to remember, but the variation of results of any yoga can be seen in the chart.

Let me give you an example from the birth chart; we all know the significator of karma is Saturn and for any human being. It is essential that one should be able to judge the highs and lows of one's career and be able to see many of the yogas forming in respect to Saturn, such as 2nd from Saturn, 3rd from Saturn, 4th from Saturn- and you can call it a technique, but in reality, this is understanding the conceptual knowledge not any technique as one simple fundamental concept of Zodiac is that one planet is always in relation to another planet such as any planet in 6th to Saturn is going to be trouble for Saturn and now we can time it via dasa or using the cycles of Bhrigu as when these two planets are going to interact with each other.

Let us do an example of the Sun in the 5th house- Sun in the 5th house gets activated at the age of 47th year, but in this year, Sun gives you the result which is extremely bad if you have Saturn in the 5th to Sun – In chart of our Late Prime Minister Smt Indira Gandhi- Sun is in 5th house but also in trine to Saturn – this was the year 1964 when her father passed away, but she was inducted in Rajya Sabha, So She lost her father, but 5th house Sun also gave position, both things are happening at the same time.

Here is the cycle of the Sun to be used, but when you use it on 20-30 charts, you will find that it is working but not able to judge the complete results as the reason being Sun don't work in isolation, The zodiac is a like a machine with multiple gears which rotate at a different speed, and then a critical point comes which is like an intersection, where two energies meet each other, and events in our life happen.

As: 27 Cn 24	Su: 4 Sc 09- DK	Mo: 5 Cp 36- GK	Ma: 16 Le 24- MK
Me: 13 Sc 15- PK	Ju (R): 15 Ta 01- PiK	Ve: 21 Sg 01- AmK	Sa: 21 Cn 48- AK
Ra: 10 Sg 35- BK	Ke: 10 Ge 35	HL: 25 Pi 47	GL: 29 Ar 19

In Bhrigu Samhita, there are charts drawn for each samvat with various variations, and results are given, but when you decode the chart, the purpose of these charts was to give straightforward reading without going into technicalities of time, but when you apply various cycles of time into zodiac you will see a pattern which you cannot miss in your reading.

All nine planets have different times w.r.t Earth as one day of Mars and one day of Sun is different, and that is why Bhrigus worked on time (Kaal). Every one of you must have heard the story of Rishi Bhrighu hitting Lord Vishnu and getting cursed by Devi Lakshmi and then by the directions of Lord Vishnu Bhrighu Samhita was created so Bhrigus on this earth can earn money via Joyitsh but let me give you an interpretation of this,

As Rishis in the bhrighu clan was trying to reach the heart of Shri Vishnu by hanging upside down this, they were defying the concept of time; all the other Rishis did penance by standing on one leg or in an asana where legs are in pain, Even when you try to sit in one posture for one time, It is legs which goes numb, Even Sanjeevani Vidhya is the knowledge again to defy time and be rejuvenated in life but as a result of the curse which story states hitting Shri Vishnu with feet is actually a symbolic one which shows that how Bhrigus capable of travelling in different realms were escaping the death by defying the concept of time.

Shukra is the only planet still upside down, making everyone in this world work to achieve the signification of Shukra; as with all the efforts in this mortal world, the end result is Shukra; even in Brighu Samhita, there is nowhere there is a division of space is happening even till now what happened to the clan of Bhrigus after this was everyone in the family had issues with legs.

The charts above belonged to people born in 1962 when Saturn was in Libra. And see, Moon is in the middle as Moon is taken as a reference in this particular Samhita, and the results are given with age-wise results and remedies. This is a classical way to read the Bhrigu Samhita, but you should start with Sun in your chart and see how results are getting manifested. You can always add/subtract the multiples of 6 to these years, and you will see the results are still valid.

Sun 1st house- 27th year

Sun 2nd house- 31st year

Sun 3rd house- 32nd year

Sun 4th house-33rd year
Sun 5th house-35th year
Sun 6th house- 29th year
Sun 7th house-34th year
Sun 8th house-30th year
Sun 9th house-34th year
Sun 10th house-31st year
Sun 11th house-33rd year
Sun 12th house-38th year.

Check-in your charts and explain in the comment section.

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SAURABH PAGDHARE

8 AUGUST 2023 AT 11:19

Thanks Sir.

My planetary positions: Kumbha lagna, sun in 4th house with retrograde mercury. Saturn in 8th house with Mars in trine to Sun.

My feedback: In my 33rd year, my daughter was born. Got a promotion at work. However, wife had slight complication while delivering (baby being wrapped in umbilical cord in neck). Also had some disagreement regarding daughter with my wife. Wife’s business declined during my 33rd year.

If I add 6, then it comes to my 39th year. I got Covid. Changed my job as I was frustrated with unrealistic expectations put in by my then boss. However got a good offer from new company.

My question: Can you please explain more about these timings and ages. How they are derived. I know about 1-12, 13-24, 25-36 cycle for each house. But these are different technique. Thanks. Much appreciated.

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